

Extraction chromatographic studies of cadmium(II) with aliquat-336

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A selective method has been developed for extraction chromatographic studies of Cd^{II} with aliquat-336 (liquid anion exchanger) coated on silica gel as a stationary phase. Quantitative extraction of Cd^{II} has been achieved with HCl at 0.05 M and onwards. The effects of different acids with varying concentrations, stripping agents, flow rate on extraction and elution have been investigated. Cd^{II} has been separated from binary, ternary and quaternary mixture of various metal ions.

Determination of cadmium in very small quantities creates problem in presence of Zn due to their identical chemical behavior¹. Extraction of cadmium from water using polyurethane foam (PUF) loaded with methyltricaprylammonium chloride (Aliquat-336) has been reported². The present study presents the results of reversed phase extraction chromatographic behavior of Cd^{II} with aliquat-336 coated on silica gel.

Results and Discussion

The extraction chromatographic behavior of Cd^{II} with aliquat-336, coated on silica gel in different acids at various concentrations showed that Cd^{II} is quantitatively extracted in HCl medium at 0.05 M and onwards. Extraction in H_2SO_4 medium was not more than 72% even at 2 M concentration. With HNO_3 , no extraction was achieved up to 4 M. 0.05 M HCl was used for extraction of Cd^{II} for further study.

Stripping agents : Different concentrations of nitric acid, sulfuric acid, hydrochloric acid, salt solutions (sodium nitrate and ammonium chloride) and deionized water were tested. It was observed that quantitative recovery of Cd^{II} is possible with HNO_3 , H_2SO_4 (up to 0.25 M) and NaNO_3 (0.5 M and onwards). Of these eluents, 0.5 M NaNO_3 gave best elution and hence used as eluent for the elution of Cd^{II} in further steps of experiment.

Separation of Cd^{II} from binary mixture : In binary mixtures with Cd^{II} in 0.05 M HCl, Th^{IV} , Pb^{II} , Co^{II} , In^{III} , Zr^{IV} , Cu^{II} , U^{VI} , Hg^{II} , Cr^{III} , Fe^{III} , Ni^{II} and Ga^{III} passed through the column with the mobile phase. Extracted Cd^{II} was, however, eluted with 0.5 M NaNO_3 and estimated complexometrically with EDTA. Binary mixtures containing Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} , Ce^{IV} and Zn^{II} were passed separately through

the column at 0.05 M HCl where all the diverse ions were co-extracted along with Cd^{II} . All the diverse ions except Pd^{II} were eluted first with demineralized water, followed by Cd^{II} with 0.5 M NaNO_3 . In case of Pd^{II} , Cd^{II} was eluted first with 0.5 M NaNO_3 followed by Pd^{II} with 6.5 M HNO_3 . After separation, metal ions were estimated complexometrically with EDTA. Extraction kinetics of Cd^{II} with respect to aliquat-336 was found to be very fast. Quantitative extraction of Cd^{II} was achieved even with the flow rate of 15 ml min^{-1} . The column containing 3 g of exchanger can uptake 45 mg (15×3) of Cd^{II} per min quantitatively.

Separation of Cd^{II} from multi-component mixtures : The results are presented Table 1. Separation of Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} was achieved by passing the mixed solution through the column at 0.05 M HCl. Only Hg^{II} passed through the column with mobile phase. Zn^{II} was eluted first with demineralized water followed by Cd^{II} with 0.5 M NaNO_3 . Separation of Cr^{III} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} was achieved by passing the ternary solution through the column at 0.05 M HCl. Only Cr^{III} passed with the mobile phase. Zn^{II} was first eluted with demineralized water followed by Cd^{II} with 0.5 M NaNO_3 . Separation of Cu^{II} , Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} was achieved by passing the mixed solution at 0.05 M HCl when Cu^{II} percolated through the column. Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} was then extracted which was eluted latter with selective eluents. Separation of Ce^{IV} , Zr^{IV} and Cd^{II} was achieved by passing the solution through the column at 0.05 M HCl. Zr^{IV} passed through the column but Ce^{IV} and Cd^{II} were extracted. Ce^{IV} was eluted with H_2O and then Cd^{II} with 0.5 M NaNO_3 .

Separation of Ce^{IV} , Zr^{IV} , Cd^{II} and Pd^{II} was achieved by passing the quaternary mixture at 0.05 M HCl. Except Zr^{IV} (which passed) all the metal ions were extracted. Ce^{IV} was eluted with demineralized water, then Cd^{II} with 0.5 M

Note

NaNO₃ and finally Pd^{II} with 6.5 M HNO₃. Separation of Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II} and Pd^{II} was achieved by passing the mixture through the column at 0.05 M HCl. Hg^{II} passed through the column but rest of the metals were extracted. Zn^{II} was eluted first with demineralized water, then Cd^{II} with 0.5 M NaNO₃ and finally Pd^{II} with 6.5 M HNO₃.

Table 1. Separation of Cd^{II} from multicomponent synthetic mixtures

Sl. no.	Metal ions in mixture	Wt. added mg	Recovery %	Relative error (%)	Eluent used	Eluent vol. (ml)
1.	Hg ^{II}	1.31	99.23	-0.77	-	25
	Zn ^{II}	2.05	99.02	-0.98	H ₂ O	30
	Cd ^{II}	1.17	100	00	0.5 M NaNO ₃	25
2.	Ce ^{III}	1.77	100.56	+0.56	-	30
	Zn ^{II}	2.05	100	00	H ₂ O	30
	Cd ^{II}	1.17	100	00	0.5 M NaNO ₃	25
3.	Cu ^{II}	1.15	99.13	-0.7	-	30
	Zn ^{II}	2.05	99.51	-0.5	H ₂ O	30
	Cd ^{II}	1.17	100.85	+0.85	0.5 M NaNO ₃	25
4.	Zr ^{IV}	1.45	102.06	+2.06	-	30
	Ce ^{IV}	1.18	101.69	+1.69	H ₂ O	30
	Cd ^{II}	1.17	99.14	-0.86	0.5 M NaNO ₃	25
5.	Zr ^{IV}	1.45	100.68	+0.68	-	30
	Ce ^{IV}	1.18	100	00	H ₂ O	30
	Cd ^{II}	1.17	99.14	-0.86	0.5 M NaNO ₃	25
	Pd ^{II}	1.05	98.09	-1.91	6.5 M HNO ₃	35
6.	Hg ^{II}	1.31	100	00	-	25
	Zn ^{II}	2.05	99.02	-0.98	H ₂ O	30
	Cd ^{II}	1.17	100.85	+0.85	0.5 M NaNO ₃	25
	Pd ^{II}	1.05	98.09	-1.91	6.5 M HNO ₃	35

Experimental

An Elico Li-120 pH meter with a combined glass electrode and a chromatographic column (Borosil) were used.

The liquid anion exchanger, aliquat-336 (Fluka, AG), a high molecular mass synthetic quaternary ammonium compound (tricaprylmethylammonium chloride) was used as such. A stock solution of Cd^{II} was prepared in distilled water and standardized complexometrically using xylenol orange as indicator⁵. The ion exchange material was prepared following literature method³. The exchange capacity of the prepared exchanger was determined as per standard method^{4,5} and was found to be 0.57 meq/g dry exchanger.

Extraction procedure : A 0.05 M HCl (20 ml) was passed through the column (0.8 × 6.5 cm) containing the prepared exchanger (3 g). An aliquat containing 1.17 mg of Cd^{II} was passed through the column at 0.05 M HCl with a flow rate 1 ml min⁻¹. After extraction, Cd^{II} was stripped with different acids, salts of various concentrations and demineralized water. A 0.5 M NaNO₃ was found to be the best stripping agent. The amount of Cd^{II} was determined complexometrically⁵.

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